

Euro-LAC Energy Teams — Insights from Science Teams on the Energy Sector Scientific Performance and Knowledge Structure Across Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean

Abstract

Understanding how science teams contribute to energy transition is essential as global energy demands rise and the environmental costs of clean technologies intensify. Science teams are increasingly central to scientific progress and innovation in the energy field. However, comparatively little is known about team-based scientific performance and thematic knowledge structures across regions, particularly between Europe and Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC). This study aims to identify and compare the scientific performance and the structural characteristics of scientific knowledge produced by research teams from Europe and LAC over the period 1996 to 2019 using a sample of 6,248 energy-related research articles sourced from Scopus. Via descriptive exploratory analysis, Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn’s post-hoc analysis, and a temporal network analysis, we show that while European science teams consistently exhibit higher normalized citation scores than their LAC counterparts, a convergence trend is emerging. We also found structural differences in research strategic and persistent priorities, with LAC emphasizing biomass and solar energy and Europe engaging more with materials science and experimental optimization. Both regions show sustained interest in bioenergy and solar-related technologies, suggesting areas for thematic complementarity. These findings provide evidence on how science team composition and regional priorities shape scientific knowledge, providing evidence to support more inclusive and strategically aligned research partnerships. The observed convergence in performance and evolving knowledge structures offer a roadmap for collaboration strategies and co-innovation between both regions.

Keywords: Science of Team Science; Energy Sector; Energy Transition; Latin America and The Caribbean; Europe

1 Introduction

Energy demands are expected to grow worldwide, from 630 exajoules in 2022 to 670 by 2030 (IEA 2023b). A single exajoule can power an average US household for 26.1 million years (EIA 2023). Meeting energy needs and addressing the environmental impact of clean energy systems poses complex challenges. Hydropower affects water and nearby ecosystems, solar and wind power require significant land use, and bioenergy production can lead to deforestation (IEA 2023a, 2023b). R&D entities such as science teams play a pivotal role in fostering innovations that will shape energy and electricity systems breakthroughs (Wu, Wang, and Evans 2019). Major trends in the science of team science (SciTS) include case studies, characteristics and dynamics, and how science teams are measured and evaluated (Li et al. 2023). For over a half century, SciTS has produced significant key insight on those and other trends, yet there is limited understanding on science teams in middle-low-income regions —such as Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC)—or comparative approaches (Y. Wang, Azcurra, and Cortes 2025; Börner et al. 2010). This is significant given the growing cooperation between Europe and LAC in clean energy transition programs (European Commission 2023). To extend on both fronts, i.e., the relationship in the energy sector between LAC and Europe and the valuable perspective of SciTS in this context, sections 1.1 and 1.2 offer a widened background on these subjects.

1.1 Related work on the energy sector in Latin America and The Caribbean and Europe

The global transition toward carbon neutrality has prompted significant reconfigurations of energy systems, particularly in Europe, where the European Green Deal sets a clear pathway toward a climate-neutral economy by 2050 (European Commission 2020; Fetting 2020). Achieving this target requires considerable deployment of renewable energy sources such as wind and solar, together with robust energy storage and grid balancing mechanisms. Technical challenges such as the occurrence of “*Dunkelflaute*” events—extended periods of low solar and wind availability—further complicate the stability of a renewable-based system (Biewald et al. 2024; Kittel and Schill 2024)

In this context, LAC emerges as a strategic partner, offering abundant solar and wind resources, large uninhabited areas suitable for renewable energy projects, and, in some countries, significant hydropower capacity. This complementarity opens opportunities for cooperation beyond traditional research partnerships, particularly in the co-development of green hydrogen economies (Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems ISE 2024; IEA 2023a; IRENA 2024). Europe has developed more mature hydrogen-related policy frameworks, yet LAC holds a comparative advantage in production potential because of favorable natural conditions and lower energy generation costs (Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems ISE 2024).

Among the promising areas for economic convergence are the production of green hydrogen and its derivatives. Electrolytic hydrogen production requires substantial inputs of clean electricity and water. Countries like Colombia, Chile, and Brazil possess strong solar irradiation, coastal wind corridors, and hydroelectric infrastructures, which create favorable conditions for cost-effective green hydrogen production (IEA 2023a). Europe will be a net importer

of hydrogen because of constraints on land use and resource availability (Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems ISE 2024).

Despite this potential, hydrogen transportation remains a significant technical challenge. Transporting compressed or liquefied hydrogen requires specialized materials and vessels because of the gas's high diffusivity and compression requirements (Berg and Rubio 2022). Most of the existing liquefied natural gas (LNG) infrastructure is not compatible with hydrogen without substantial retrofitting, increasing costs, and complicating logistics. As a workaround, green hydrogen can be converted into ammonia, which is easier to store and transport and has a dual-use value as an energy carrier and a fertilizer input. This dual role presents a strategic advantage for countries like Colombia, which currently depend on imported fertilizers and are seeking to build domestic fertilizer production capacity. By investing in green ammonia, LAC countries could supply their agricultural sectors while exporting surpluses to Europe, creating a value-added chain anchored in local development and global decarbonization.

1.2 Related work on Science of Team Science (SciTS)

Energy transition requires rapid decarbonization, systemic efficiency improvements, and fair access to clean energy (IPCC 2022). Meeting energy needs and addressing the environmental impact of energy transition poses complex challenges. Beyond technological innovation, these challenges also require robust interdisciplinary collaboration of science teams. SciTS plays a pivotal role in understanding how these collaborative networks form, operate, and produce innovations that will shape energy and electricity systems breakthroughs (Wu, Wang, and Evans 2019). Science teams have proven effective in sustainability-related fields because they bridge disciplinary divides that often hinder progress (McGreavy et al. 2015). Effective teams in energy research often blend technical expertise (like renewable energy engineers and grid specialists), social science viewpoints (such as energy justice scholars and policy analysts), local knowledge holders (including community energy practitioners), and industry stakeholders (Hall et al. 2012, 2018). Key factors driving research impact and innovation cycles of energy transition studies—according to empirical SciTS analysis—are well-structuration, demographic diversity, interdisciplinary collaboration, and geographic representation (Hall et al. 2012; Stvilia et al. 2010; Batz-Lineiro 2020). These advantages are accompanied by managerial challenges, including property disputes and the steep learning curve inherent in establishing shared terminology and methodologies within interdisciplinary teams (McGreavy et al. 2015; Falk-Krzyszinski et al. 2011).

The growing cooperation between LAC and Europe in energy transition programs provides a compelling framework for exploring science team dynamics (European Commission 2023). Yet, knowledge gaps persist regarding the influence of science teams' composition on the results of energy research conducted in different institutional and geopolitical environments (Bouabid and Achachi 2022). In developing countries, where resource constraints and institutional challenges may impede collaborative efforts, science team productivity and innovation can be maximized by policymakers prioritizing team dynamics, diversity, and team-build strategies. Therefore, this research seeks to address two research questions (RQ_n):

RQ₁: How do science teams' region of affiliation influence the scientific performance of teams and organizations in LAC and Europe in the field of energy?

RQ₂: How has the structure of scientific knowledge produced by teams and organizations in LAC and Europe in the field of energy unfolded?

In sum, this study aims to identify and compare the scientific performance and the structural characteristics of scientific knowledge produced by research teams from Europe and LAC over the period 1996 to 2019. Building on these findings, science policy institutions and energy agencies may employ the findings to inform the design of SciTS funding programs, foster more inclusive and effective science teams, and develop strategies to optimize the use of resources to produce scientific and innovation breakthroughs in energy-related fields. Moreover, the results could guide evidence-based policy interventions aimed at strengthening international cooperation, beyond LAC-Europe. After this introduction, we extend our methodology. Then, we discussed the results under the light of previous literature and concluded the study with the conclusions, limitations, and future research agenda.

2 Methodology

2.1 Materials

We sourced bibliographic metadata from one of the canonical bibliographic data bases: Scopus, which provide a high-quality—although with language-geographical coverage limitations—of the world's scientific output (Baas et al.

2020). We extracted research papers published in journals with the subject area ‘energy’ between 1996 and 2019, with each paper listing at least one author from both LAC and Europe as coauthors. We truncated the query in 2019 to leave a 5-year window—a standard in bibliometric evaluations when assessing performance (J. Wang 2013). The analysis proceeded with 6,248 articles after excluding those without DOIs or citations. The average annual output is ~263 articles and the average growth is ~12%¹.

2.2 Software

We used R statistical language (R Core Team 2021), RStudio (RStudio Team 2020), as well as the following packages: igraph (Csárdi et al. 2006), data.table (Barrett et al. 2006), ggpubr (Kassambara 2016), and openxlsx (Schauberger and Walker 2014).

2.3 Variables definition

- Team: a group of 2 to 10 individuals who are involved in a project (i.e., a research paper) (National Research Council 2015).
- Organization: a group of over 10 individuals (National Research Council 2015).
- Region: we defined a group’s regional classification when > 50% of the total country affiliations are from countries within a specific (sub)continent; otherwise (no country’s majority), it is categorized as a ‘Multinational’ team.
- Scientific performance: we used the mean normalized citation score (MNCS) (Bornmann and Wohlrabe 2019), calculated by dividing the actual count of citations of each article (i.e., team or organization) by the average citation for articles of the same year of publication and subject area. A MNCS value above 1.0 suggests that an article has a higher-than-expected performance. There is a significant and strong correlation between MNCS, and full citation counts ($\rho = .98, S = 755875008, p < .001$).

2.4 Methods

2.4.1 Team composition and performance

We conducted a descriptive exploratory analysis on variables such as team’s size, region, and performance. We also conducted a Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn’s post-hoc analysis to identify performance differences between LAC-Europe teams and organizations.

2.4.2 Mapping the knowledge structure evolution

To model the knowledge structure produced by teams and organizations in LAC-Europe throughout 1996–2019, we implemented an approach based on co-occurrence and temporal network analysis (Cortés and Ramírez Cajiao 2024; Cortés 2022). Teams were segmented into regional subsets (LAC, Europe, Multinational). To facilitate temporal analysis, each sub-set was divided into five distinct 5-year periods: 1996–2000, 2001–2005, 2006–2010, 2011–2015, and 2016–2019. Subsequently, keyword co-occurrence networks were constructed for each five-year subset of articles. For each period, all possible pairs of co-occurring keywords—forming an edge list—were identified based on their joint appearance within the same publication. Keyword pairs that appeared fewer than five times were excluded to ensure that only meaningful co-occurrence relationships were retained. Each edge list was transformed into an undirected graph (Csárdi and Nepusz 2006). Then, a co-word network was modeled. It is formalized as follows:

$$B_{cn} = A^T A$$

Where B_{cn} represents the co-word adjacency matrix, A is the document-term matrix, where rows correspond to documents and columns correspond to keywords and A^T is the transpose of the document-term matrix. The

¹Search query for replication: *AFFILCOUNTRY (mexico OR brazil OR "brasil" OR colombia OR chile OR argentina OR ecuador OR venezuela OR peru OR cuba OR uruguay OR "costa rica" OR "puerto rico" OR bolivia OR guatemala OR paraguay OR nicaragua OR panama OR "dominican republic" OR "republica dominicana" OR honduras OR "el salvador") AND AFFILCOUNTRY (germany OR france OR spain OR españa OR italy OR netherlands OR belgium OR sweden OR norway OR denmark OR finland OR portugal OR greece OR austria OR switzerland OR poland OR "czech republic" OR hungary OR ireland OR croatia OR slovakia OR slovenia OR latvia OR lithuania OR estonia OR romania OR bulgaria OR cyprus OR malta OR luxembourg OR albania OR andorra OR armenia OR azerbaijan OR belarus OR "bosnia and herzegovina" OR iceland OR moldova OR monaco OR montenegro OR "north macedonia" OR "san marino" OR serbia OR "vatican city" OR turkey OR georgia OR kazakhstan OR kosovo OR russia OR ukraine OR "united kingdom" OR "wales" OR "scotland") AND PUBYEAR > 1995 AND PUBYEAR < 2020 AND SRCTYPE(j) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar")) AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"ENER"))*

multiplication $A^T A$ results in a co-occurrence matrix where each entry represents the number of times two keywords co-occur within the same articles (Aria and Cuccurullo 2017).

Betweenness centrality was computed for each keyword within its respective period. It is formalized as follows:

$$C_B(p_k) = \sum_{i < j}^n \frac{g_{ij}(p_k)}{g_{ij}}, \text{ where } i \neq j \neq k$$

Where $C_B(p_k)$ represents the betweenness centrality of node p_k , g_{ij} is the total number of the shortest paths between nodes p_i and nodes p_j , $g_{ij}(p_k)$ is the number of shortest paths between nodes p_i and nodes p_j that pass through p_k . The summation runs over all pairs of nodes (i, j) such that $i \neq j \neq k$ (Opsahl, Agneessens, and Skvoretz 2010). Betweenness centrality quantifies the influence of a node in facilitating communication or flow of information within the graph, acting as a bridge between different clusters (Freeman 1977). In our context, keywords with high betweenness play a key role in linking different topics or themes. Raw betweenness scores were min-max normalized, rescaling values between 0 and 1 while preserving relative differences.

To identify keywords with structural significance over time, the top 100 keywords across all periods combined. A keyword was deemed stable if it appeared in the top 100 ranking both within at least one period and in the overall ranking. We used the Blondel et al. (2008) modularity algorithm to group frequently co-occurrent keywords. Then, we tasked ChatGPT (OpenAI 2025) with labeling the six most crowded clusters (~90% of the nodes) based on the top five keywords with highest betweenness centrality. We displayed the results by teams and organization regions faceted by thematic clusters in streamgraphs to illustrate the changing structure relevance of consistent keywords from 1996 to 2019 (Mauri et al. 2017). Note that streams appearing below zero do not indicate negative values but rather represent categories with lower relative betweenness centrality compared to the dominant category in each given period

3 Results

Concerning RQ₁, there is a balanced regional composition between Europe (~36%) and LAC (~36%) teams and organizations. Teams are the dominant collaboration structure across all years, consistently representing over 89% and often exceeding 95% of collaborations in any year. Organizations make up a small but consistent minority, typically ranging from 1% to 7% annually, increasing since 2012 (Fig. 1—A). Since 2005, a marked expansion has been observed in these collaborative initiatives. From 2015 onward, a significant expansion of team collaborations has been observed, suggesting an alteration in the dynamics of team conformation. European teams systematically present a larger average size than those in LAC (Fig. 1—B). When it comes to scientific performance (Fig. 1—C), the general trend shows that European teams and organizations consistently maintain a higher MNCS than LAC, suggesting a higher relative scientific visibility and influence. Nevertheless, a certain convergence has been observed in recent years, particularly during periods when the MNCS of Europe exhibits a slight decline, while that of LAC remains stable or experiences moderate growth.

Fig. 1 Number of collaboration types: individual, team, or organization (A); team average size by region (B); and MNCS (performance) of teams by region (C) from 1996 to 2019.

A Kruskal-Wallis test was conducted to examine differences in mean performance across four organizational regions: Europe, LAC, Multinational (~25%), and North America (~1%) teams and organizations (Fig. 2). The test revealed a statistically significant difference in MNCS between the regions. Significant differences were found between Europe and LAC; LAC and Multinational; and LAC and North America. The median performance values were .90 for North America (although this is based on a small sample), .70 for Europe, .67 for Multinational, and .61 for LAC. These results suggest that the distribution of performance varies significantly across organizational regions, with North America exhibiting the highest median performance and LAC the lowest. However, the size effect of these groups differences is small, $\eta^2_{ordinal} = .01$.

Fig. 2 Kruskal-Wallis test of teams and organization scientific performance (i.e., MNCS) across regions.

Regarding RQ₂, Fig. 3 displays the streamgraph for LAC teams and Fig. 4 for European ones. While the topics “Biomass Conversion and Renewable Energy Processes,” “Sustainable Carbon Management and Optimization,” and “Mathematical Modeling in Energy” held greater structural importance in LAC before gaining prominence in Europe, the latter cluster has since become more relevant in Europe while diminishing on the LAC agenda. In contrast, European research teams engaged earlier with “Experimental Studies in Biofuel and Energy” and “Material Characterization and Microscopy Techniques” compared to their LAC counterparts. Notably, in both regions, the “Experimental Studies in Biofuel and Energy” cluster contained the most persistent keywords, followed by “Sustainable Carbon Management and Optimization.” Regarding long-term keyword persistence, BIOMASS’ (Biomass Conversion and Renewable Energy Processes) was the only term consistently present across all analyzed periods in LAC. Meanwhile, in Europe, the persistent keywords were ‘FERMENTATION’ (Experimental Studies in Biofuel and Energy) and ‘OXIDATION’ (Material Characterization and Microscopy Techniques). It is important to highlight that many emerging high-betweenness keywords from the most recent analysis period do not overlap

between the two regions. For instance, “MASS SPECTROMETRY” and “THERMAL POWER” emerged in Europe, while “FOSSIL FUELS” gained prominence in LAC. The only recent keywords of structural significance common to both regions are “SOLAR ENERGY” and “SOLAR CELLS” (Mathematical Modeling in Energy).

Fig. 3 Streamgraphs of persistent keywords with higher betweenness centrality by thematic clusters from 1996 to 2019 — LAC. Note: streams appearing below zero do not indicate negative values but rather represent categories with lower relative betweenness centrality compared to the dominant category in each given period.

Fig. 4 Streamgraphs of persistent keywords with higher betweenness centrality by thematic clusters from 1996 to 2019 — Europe. Note: streams appearing below zero do not indicate negative values but rather represent categories with lower relative betweenness centrality compared to the dominant category in each given period.

4 Discussion and conclusion

This study aimed to identify and compare the scientific performance and the structural characteristics of scientific knowledge produced by research teams from Europe and LAC over the period 1996 to 2019. Based on the results, our analysis shows a crucial role for teams, as opposed to organizations. The last five years, however, have seen a rise in the significance of organizations. This finding reinforces the growing dominance of teams in science. The average team size has more than doubled since the 1970s (from 1.9 to 3.5 members), a trend attributable to reduced communication costs, increased workforce specialization in knowledge frontiers, and the rise of large-scale projects (i.e., *big science*) in areas such as high-energy physics and biomedicine (Wuchty, Jones, and Uzzi 2007; Ioannidis, Cristea, and Boyack 2020; de Solla Price 1963).

Global North's historical performance advantage keeps its edge, yet it appears to be fading. Geography plays a significant role in supporting this line of thought. The performance of research teams, measured in terms of citation flows, as well as the strength of collaboration between authors in different cities, decrease with greater separation (Pan, Kaski, and Fortunato 2012).

Considering the substantial differences in continental area (i.e., Europe: ~10 million km²; LAC: ~19 million km²), which affect the geographic proximity between scientific teams in Europe and LAC, these variables appear to be even

more relevant (World Population Review 2025). Furthermore, the considerable differences in investment in R&D between both regions (LAC 0.6% of GDP, while Europe 2.3%) makes it very difficult for science teams mostly in LAC to do better than the world average in terms of availability of resources to drive scientific performance (Pan, Kaski, and Fortunato 2012; The World Bank 2022). European science teams, located in a world leading region in science, enjoy a cumulative advantage (Merton 1968) compared to other Global South regions such as LAC, where the national science systems are still turning academics into researchers (Vasen et al. 2023). This produces that leading countries in science receive more citations than others conducting similar thematic research, deepening the already substantial inequalities in science despite remarkable scientific progress made in *peripheral* countries and scientific teams (Gomez, Herman, and Parigi 2022; Cortés and Andrade 2022).

Structural topic modeling of regional science teams showed that these differences in scientific focus offer both challenges and opportunities for cooperation. First, the divergence of emerging high-betweenness topics suggests scientific agendas are currently shaped by different government and science policy contextual imperatives and capacities. Second, they also open space for complementarity: LAC early and persistent focus on biomass and solar energy may be leveraged in combination with European advancements in materials science and experimental optimization techniques. Joint research programs that bridge these topical differences could significantly enhance the innovation ecosystem on both sides of the Atlantic, particularly in areas such as solar-to-hydrogen conversion, materials for electrolysis, and integrated bioenergy systems.

Lessons from past energy technology adoption in LAC can also inform the design of future cooperation. For example, bioenergy research in Brazil experienced a significant boom between 2004 and 2016—as seen in Fig. 3—, particularly around sugarcane ethanol and biomass-to-power technologies. However, this momentum did not translate into widespread regional adoption, partly because of institutional fragmentation and varying degrees of policy support (IEA 2023a). In Europe, while bioenergy remains part of the renewable portfolio, its scalability has been limited by social resistance and environmental concerns, particularly regarding land use competition with food crops and forest conservation (IEA 2024; IPCC 2022). This contrast underscores the need for socially sensitive and environmentally coherent technology transfers. Cooperation should thus be oriented not merely toward exporting technologies but toward co-creating solutions that address local needs and conditions.

The concept of energy security adds another layer to this cooperation. Europe’s increasing reliance on variable renewable energy creates systemic vulnerability, particularly during *Dunkelflaute* events, which typically occur during winter and affect large geographical areas simultaneously, limiting the effectiveness of spatial balancing (Biewald et al. 2024; Kittel and Schill 2024). Current battery technologies offer short-duration storage—ranging from 1 to 5 hours—while *Dunkelflaute* periods can last several days. Long-duration storage options, such as hydrogen, are therefore essential to ensure grid stability. However, the scale of hydrogen storage required is not yet feasible within Europe’s territorial and regulatory constraints.

Therefore, Europe’s long-term energy resilience may depend, in part, on reliable hydrogen imports from partner regions. From this perspective, LAC could serve not just as an energy supplier but as an integral part of Europe’s energy security architecture (Fraunhofer Institute for Solar Energy Systems ISE 2024). Such a relationship would need to be grounded in mutual benefit and long-term institutional arrangements, avoiding extractive dynamics that have historically characterized North–South resource exchanges. Policy frameworks must include safeguards for labor rights, environmental protection, and community participation to ensure that hydrogen economies are socially inclusive and environmentally. A joint effort between European and LAC agencies to establish interoperable certification systems could facilitate trade, attract investment, and ensure transparency in sustainability claims.

The limitations of this study may lie in the simplification of regional classifications, which do not account for intra-regional heterogeneity (e.g., differences between Brazil and Bolivia in scientific development), and in the overreliance on citation analysis, without considering indicators of technological advancement such as patent activity or the wider adoption of energy-related innovations (e.g., solar cells). Furthermore, additional characteristics of scientific teams—such as gender composition, disciplinary diversity, and academic experience—should be examined in greater depth. A deeper understanding of migration, mobility, and co-authorship dynamics may also contribute to insights into brain drain, brain gain, and brain circulation phenomena. Additionally, the inclusion of socio-economic variables and the role of cross-sector collaborations could offer a more comprehensive perspective on the knowledge base of the energy sector.

Authors contribution

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